

WHAT TO SAY ABOUT MINKOWSKI'S "LOSS OF VITAL CONTACT WITH REALITY"?

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Abstract: This brief paper has the main objective of presenting in general terms our interpretation and description of Minkowski's famous text, which significantly defined his intellectual trajectory - the *The notion of loss of vital contact with reality and its applications in psychopathology* (1926). The entire linguistic fabric of this paper shows how the author, in a special and unique way, sees the interpretation of this text and its consequences. This means that what will be stated here does not closely and necessarily follow a phenomenological psychopathology of the loss of vital contact with reality. However, in the light of a personal interpretation, the author tries to somehow consider what Minkowski may have thought when writing this specific text. For the purpose of deepening and interpretative coherence, our text contains a personal analysis (self-analysis) in which the author experienced the aforementioned "loss of vital contact with reality". Furthermore, we conclude that the vital reality of life being of absolute presence par excellence, we are all in some way inside or outside this "vital reality" subject at all times to a change in our psychological and, why not, pathological states.

Keywords: Loss. Contact. Vital. Reality. Minkowski.

Eugène Minkowski: an introduction

Eugène Minkowski (1886-1972), renowned French psychiatrist of the 19th century, was for us (and still is and will be for a long time) *an extraordinary figure*. His work as a psychotherapist is unique and singular, mainly in relation to one of his main analyzes of the existential contour of reality - namely - *the loss of vital contact with her*. Normally, as "healthy" thinking minds, we live and experience the world around us. *world-environment* in a common, everyday and even sometimes very *automatic*. Wake up, take a shower, have coffee, go to work and rest. Thus, the issue is not in the order or hierarchy of these routine and very monotonous activities, but, above all, in the way of seeing and, even more specifically, in the *way of thinking* these activities. to, finally, execute them and, mainly, *know how to relate* with the field of possibilities that existential life offers us. Therefore, as we know very consciously, this entire flow of activities is already part of our existential being because, from an early age, in the first stages of childhood, we were already, in an ontogenetic and ontological way, accustomed to carrying out all those actions in the fabric of the

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human being. time in the history of our lives. It turns out that Minkowski (1926 [2004]) does not want to show us, above all, this uniform fabric or this same or even distressing symmetry of the ordinary life of each of us. On the contrary, as a psychotherapist, he alerts us to an important emergency that can happen or appear precisely when carrying out these small and simple activities or everyday tasks.

Therefore, from the figure of the magnanimous Heidegger (1889-1976), above all, given his masterful contribution to our lives as human beings, namely, *Being and time*, the entire scenario or structure of psychiatry, above all, *breaks* in the sense that we, as psychotherapists, *review* all psychopathological clinical cases with a *new look*, mainly due to the *changing the spirit of History* (to use a term from Hegel). Well, in my opinion, it was the radical change of *spirit of history* which made Heidegger, already in the 20th century, in 1927, systematize a “theory” of *existence* so that we, above all, *alert* that all patients (or all of us) should become aware of the way *our meaningful relationships* with space and time must in any case *shape us* and even *direct us* retrospectively or prospectively towards a capital outcome that will culminate in absolute certainty in the *be-to-death*. We want to say that, while “death” does not appear or does not come, every human being-there *be-played* inside a really *game* (existence), without being able to escape in any way, doomed to the fate of *gets involved* with good relationships; with the anguish and natural agony of the world of things itself or even with the mystery of not knowing what else to do in this life and falling into a dark abyss of *Nothing*. Furthermore, for *be-played*, as long as the total outcome or the total succumbing of your physical-matter-existential body does not occur, the significant relationships with space and time will survive even after the catastrophic end of the *perish*.

It was precisely this existence that Minkowski (1926 [2004]) knew very well how to “repair” (I mean “visualize”) in a very detailed and precise way. However, Minkowski is much more of a psychopathologist than Heidegger himself, as the latter aims to demonstrate more theoretically (and abstractly) *as material existence* (above all) *and*; whereas, for the former, the main goal was *to understand* and *describe* everything that *cause* to being, in the presence or absence of vital contact with this vital reality that is Life. In this way, whether the being is present or not, in this reality, he will, in any case, demonstrate, during his earthly or existential life, “abnormal” behaviors or behaviors close to non-normativity in the face of everyday life (or if you want to prefer, psychopathological behavior at first sight). It is, then, the framework or insertion-into-the-game-of-reality that will define the psychopathological contour or not with this reality. In an article² Recently, I described, in general terms, that all of us, as human beings, are doomed to all types of relationships because we are absorbed by a condition, although natural, but “psychopathological” of this world of ours; what is the *hallucinatory (or hallucinatory) spirit of the*

² SANTOS, C. *The immaterial side of hallucination*. Zenodo, 1-8, 2024.

world. I wanted to say that, in my simple view, every act of survival in this life is surrounded or even “contaminated” concretely or not with the wounds of the *mind-blowing spirit of the world*. Because, in very short terms, the world, this one of ours, *hallucinate!* And it is, in the face of this absolute presence of hallucination in the world, that we become ill, seriously or not, but everyone together also hallucinates!

To recall a term by Émile Benveniste (1902-1976), the *Me-Here-Now (Me-Here-Now)*, the same Minkowski does this, however, *psychology* our relationship with these three dimensions, while the former uses it with the intention of building a *theory of enunciation*. Minkowski, in addition to also being concerned with what is said, with everything that is enunciated by being-there-human, is also concerned with the interrelational way of this being with *space and time*. Since then, Minkowski's idea was to realize in short words that - space in us *gets sick*, as well as the time *gets sick*, taking into account today's world, *technique!* However, the nature of space and time are perfect, but everything will essentially depend on our relationship with these two dimensions that, in this world, synthesize material existence.

The significance of the expression “loss of vital contact with reality”

In the text “The loss of vital contact with reality and its applications in psychopathology”, Minkowski (1926 [2004]) presents us precisely with what we stated in general terms in the previous topic - which are the relationships with the *space* and the *time* the root cause of a series of psychopathologies. The expression “loss of vital contact with reality” in itself already presents us with a certain and unique type of psychopathology, among them, *schizophrenia*. Being, in the vision of its totality, is absolutely *complex* and, in addition, *singular*. But, following a phenomenological thought in the immanence of the meaning of this expression, we can say, without fear, that - each act, let us repeat, each act, physical or psychic, that is, our current freedom to act, delimits, influences and even defines, the from our psychological reactions, the human being that we are or will be. Thus, given this fact, the phenomenological psychopathology of the loss of vital contact with reality, if we were to define it in very simple terms, would be - everything that the being absorbs from vital contact with reality, namely, every type of relationship that or be already *means* in the relationship with the world. It would then be the *being-not-world* or the *being-no-world*. Every act of survival in the world shapes every psychological state of being; like this; *the psychological value of the psychic energy of the being's libido* (to use a term from Jung (2002)) comes to define, with this particular flow of energy, the type of psychosis that the individual will have.

“Loss” means “absence”; “contact” - “relationship” and “reality” - in this case - just the “physical-material”. It turns out that, although Minkowski did not weave his psychological theory with “metaphysical colors”; even so; the value of your psychology is also *metaphysical*. Why? Simply because the great fabric surrounding the loss of vital contact is Reality; thus, this particular reality is, moreover, the entire reality of all the possibilities of all things. What this means is that although the fabric or appearance of the clear surface of reality tells us something, there is therefore, subterraneanly, *the dark side of reality* and it is in these depths of yours that the psychopathologist finds the very cause or even the origin of other or new psychological disorders - if the loss of vital contact with reality goes beyond an effective “reality”, a “disease”. Although, in the complex language of esoteric reality, “losing oneself” from reality would not really be a disease, but much more a particular way of being, in addition to seeing a new possibility of “deviation” or a new “opening ” in his life, is a sagacious and even divine form of a purpose to live from the spiritual substance of things, namely, the *supraworld*.

In this way, every act is a “detour”, that is, it causes a reopening of the field of possibilities of existence. Let us repeat - “each act”. In other words, if we are faced here with a phenomenological psychopathology, Phenomenology itself made us believe that it is in each act of consciousness (or even the synthesis of this act that is the *unconscious darkness*) that infinite transformations of infinite and unique realities will appear. An important point that we witness here - Minkowski drank from the French Bergsonian source, mainly from the philosophy of *he argues vigorously*. For us, it is precisely from this specific point that Minkowski begins to understand and clarify the nuances of each type of diagnosis or the particular and living soul of each individual. “Élan vital” means “vital impulse” and because it is “vital” it originates both in the very nature of existence with its “cosmic-sensitive impulse” (the “psychosensoriality” of Nature or the Cosmos), and in the nature of each being. human which, in an ontological and ontogenetic way, is properly an “impulse always forward and upward”. Thus, the “synthesis” of the two, *to be* and *world*, highlights the nature of each type of psychopathology. Only the sensorimotor universe is one of these syntheses. If in every psychic act of the individual and in every psychic act of Nature there dwells and is “hidden” an “impulse”; What can we say, then, about a multiform and infinite series of a dizzying multiplicity of impulses, both on the part of Nature's production and on the part of the individual.

It's from this *he argues vigorously* that every individual *awaken* for life, now, always in tune (or in absolute connection) with all the impulses or stimuli of the Reality of Nature. Because, as you well know, Nature is Reality and it is this “reality” that Minkowski enunciates. It turns out that Minkowski had understood that when an individual *lose* vital contact with reality, this means that he has simply lost the *vitality of life* more than the world and then *it lost*, whether important or not, the

he argues vigorously originating naturally from life, from existential reality. When this happens, not only does it lose a large portion of the conscious synthesis of the world and its relationships, but it is absorbed almost completely by another type of reality that is not external, but internal. Even if in this depth of your interiority a world similar and parallel to the external world emerges and takes place (because the external shapes the internal and vice versa), the internal world is the only world now possible, since all or almost all relationships with the outside, reality, were cut off, leaving only my intimacy with myself, that is, *absolute introspection*. Thus, by losing vital contact with reality, one loses precisely what supported one's world and, therefore, by losing such architecture, one loses psychophysical orientation in relation to the external world. In this way, each act in consciousness is no longer towards what is in front of me, in my field of vision, but each act, being purely introspective, only points, or rather, only internalizes itself more and more inward. As a result of this condition, psychopathologies arise, such as, for example, *melancholy* or, in more serious situations, the *schizophrenia*.

Thus, one of the psychopathological conditions of schizophrenia (or of the patient *schizo*) is precisely *the loss of vital contact with reality*. In fact, this is one of the first symptoms or signs inherent in this being. Because of occurrences connected to relationships even during childhood (Oedipus complex, castration or sublimation) or the existential condition in which that individual finds himself (or found himself) awakens in him episodes of ghostly appearances of strange objects such as himself, mother, son or daughter, or even himself and all possible objects in this world. The state of the schizophrenic being could be clarified in the metaphor of the mirror to the individual *schizo* see his spectrum before him and realize that, perhaps or without a shadow of a doubt, there he is no longer himself, but a new being. What happens in this example is that the *schizo* remains himself and he continues to believe that that reflection is himself, despite the real existence of abrupt changes that are occurring deep within him, but one thing is the vision (or perception) of the world itself. *schizo* and the other is the psychopathologist's view. The individual thus loses not only his identity (because he has lost vital contact with the world), but he loses the direction and/or orientation of his own being. Therefore, being subjectively confused and his relationships with the world being confused, the experience of his psyche (or "living soul") is totally "intoxicated" also by this "deviation in conduct" in relation to the world and his own.

If we were to summarize all psychopathologies in a single, but decisive word, it would be "disorder". And what Minkowski precisely proves about this "disorder" is that it is influenced and even defined by the relationships between the individual's being and the world. Thus, it is no coincidence that Heidegger uses the terms *being-not-world* and *being-no-world* that, in fact, Medard Boss and Ludwig Binswanger, have noticed in this one of the causes of the great variety of terms referring to the *Detour* or to *disorder* psychological, creating the *Analysis of existence*, which,

supported by Heideggerian thought, is also a *theory of knowledge* or even a *science*, a subarea of Phenomenology.

The individual is born and, at birth, beforehand, even unconsciously, he “gets sick” because, as we say in the previous topic, the world itself *distress* and *hallucinates* and what about *being and being-in-the-world*. Out of curiosity and study, I wrote a book (*e-book*)³ called *Existential metaphysical anguish* in which I delve deeper into this topic of *being and being-in-the-world* against the backdrop of the state of *be-distressed-no-world*. In it, I argue with arguments that, esoterically speaking, the world *and* anguish.

It seems not, but, temporally speaking, this world of ours is like a clock, as it even symmetrically follows the lines of events and escape of its own *Interiority*. Space is not time that counts or passes, but, in space, the order of events occurs in the synthesis of their spatiality with that of time. Time flows and space flows along with time. Yes, space exists by itself, but that which causes its movement, not to be *empty* and “*static*”, it's time. In this way, time *open* and space *covered*, in this synthesis of movement. Therefore, it is in this indivisible flow that the relations of the human being-there-are *built*. It turns out that there is a problem - time next to space gives existence a perfect order that is natural, but the human being, in his anguish and consequent ontological confusion of being just “human”, “disorders”, or that is, “interprets” that order as an “order”, but which, in truth, that is, substantially speaking, is a “disorder”. It's just that if we talk to Buddhists, everything here is nothing more than an illusion because everything is, in addition, *ephemerality*. So, it is in view of this perspective, which is actually true and fundamental, that the human being is *absorbed* excellently and truly by the world of things created by God, but *absorb* in a way that is almost completely contrary to all things in this created world. This is why we say that human beings do not create, but *co-create* simply because such Creation has already been made or consummated.

Thus, in the logical order of facts, the vital reality of existence unfolds in a thousand marvels, it turns out that, faced with this perfect and natural order, man, even with his intellect created and perfected by a divine order, does what (?), *detract!* Therefore, there is an uninterrupted game of actualities and virtualities, that is, at the moment a thing or a situation is current it has already been, in some way, *virtualized*; and the moment it is virtual it has already been *updated*. It is by following this “order-disorder” that a multiplicity of psychopathologies end up emerging. Because, dear reader, what lies behind all psychopathology is, in fact, *the way we interpret* the world and, along these lines, also *how we mean it*. See, then; what; what is still behind is the *sense*, not the sense of Viktor Frankl, but *the meaning of one's own existence*, i.e, *the substance* which originates from our vital contact with the reality that *draw* and *surface* all the psychological values

³ SANTOS, C. *Angústia metafísica existencial*. Pará de Minas: VirtualBooks, 2024.

of our psyche (or “soul”). It is, then, in the encounter with this “order-disorder” that the individual can, at a given moment or several in their life, become ill. Therefore, we want to say, once again, that Nature is perfect in its excellence; It turns out that it’s not that we were born “sick” beforehand, it’s that the very process and manifestation of something called “meaning” can lead us either towards good or towards evil. The mind is perfect, it is a powerful “machine”; although, as Deleuze (1972 [2011]) always told us and warned us - “there is in us and in the world around us a schizophrenia, and this schizophrenia is a *schizophrenia of the senses*”.

In this sense, it seems that we are doomed to the Lord of Time because if the temporalization of time itself is *a multiple disorder of meanings and significance*, what can we say, then, about all our conscious (or psychic or psychological) acts which passed through the channel of a consciousness, by nature, double (?). The vital substance of life is life, and if we are in/with life, we are subject to absolutely every kind of deviation, rupture and even “disorder”. So, perhaps, *the loss of vital contact with reality* by Minkowski is, in fact, a sign or a warning that we are all subject to becoming human beings *schizo* when, at every moment and in every event, we lose track of what life is, consequently losing track of reality and what we do or will do. Finally, I emphasize that, in this article, I am not trying to deal with a phenomenological psychopathology of the loss of vital contact with reality, but rather to infer a possible interpretative reality of what, I think, Minkowski may have thought about.

Psychological-phenomenological self-analysis about my psychopathology

From a very early age, in my early childhood, I was always an extremely *introspective*. Today I know that this particularity of mine has caused me, in some aspects of my life, wonders, but also disenchantment (and very serious psychic comorbidities). I was born on the 27th and, following a spiritual aspect, $2+7$ is equivalent to 9; 9 is the number of high spirituality. And, given all the very tragic events in my life, perhaps it was this high level of spirituality since the creation of the substance of my being that sustained me, comforted me and even cured me of many psychological illnesses. Given these events of mine, for this article, I will take just one, which is the one referring to *to my loss of vital contact with reality*.

Around the beginning of January 2015, I, as a teacher, asked to leave a school where I taught. Reason: beginning of depression. I had and still have an extremely authoritarian father who only prohibits everything I do and even (incredible as it may seem) everything I think. Summary: my father doesn't accept who I am! I grew up with this extremely negative relationship on my father's part and I even contracted, because of crystallized emotions about him and the fear he caused me, a stutter. From then on, I began to gradually stay away from the spotlight, that is, away

from everything worldly. My relationships with friends were no longer a reality and I decided for myself to move away from everything and everyone. So, I closed myself at home and closed all the doors to everything external to me.

So, as I was already an extremely introspective being, I became even more so, causing a great break with the world; *the absolute closure of the external world* and the ever more “ferocious” and tireless opening within myself. So, at this point in my life, it was just me, me and myself. Even though we know that the world exists in front of us, it is as if the only world that actually and presently existed was my internal world. It was from this that the flow of my thoughts began to work only from the inside to the inside; in dizzyingly introspective madness.

Within this only world that was mine, after some time, I realized that the only and “best” companion I had were just two simple things: my thoughts and my cigarette. Thus, each puff of cigarette instantly gave rise to a new thought. And so it was for many years, approximately a decade living solely on my thoughts. In the meantime, I discovered fantastic things about this fantastic world of God; I read, without a shadow of a doubt, hundreds of authors ranging from Linguistics, Psychology and Philosophy to Esotericism. I can't be sure how many entire books I have read with great attention and dedication, but my bookshelf alone has more or less around 500 books, not counting the dozens or even hundreds of books that I have read so far. PDF via computer or *Kindle*.

It turns out that I read to forget or even “cure” myself from that depression since 2015. However, it turns out that (and this I believe), I spent a lot of time paying attention and reading many works and articles on Phenomenology, mainly Husserl. I have even xeroxed Husserl's phenomenological approaches to fantasy. Well, this theme of the human imagination moved and surprised me a lot. I believe that, together with my sad depression and reading a lot of extremely abstract things about our relationship with objects in the world (whether inanimate or animate objects), I started to follow the panpsychist approach and not just that; my mind became “panpsychist”. I then began to have a perception or a feeling that everything was interconnected, all things, and more, all these things, whether an animal, a human or a table, had a “soul”.

I went to the psychiatrist a few times and he diagnosed me with “self-sabotage”, because I told him that I think that everything, absolutely everything, has a *sense*. So, within each act of a new possibility, I saw “meaning”, not forgetting that I was still living and at the same time experiencing only the things in my “little world”; the internal world. It was when, around a certain time, from living so much only from *food* of my own thoughts, once and for all excluding external reality, which I realized *I had lost my vital contact with reality*.

Given this, the impression that seemed true to me; was that all external reality no longer existed, as all relationships with it were *cut*, transforming the space and time of this reality into the space and time of myself, of my internal reality. With this, that concrete and ordinary substance of

the world would become *dissolving* more and more until it removes the envelope from the appearance of the world. It was just me and myself. It came at a certain point in my life that this external reality had begun to lose its vitality so much for me, that my contact with this world began to be full of psychoses, paranoia, persecutory delusions and various hallucinations.

In this sense, the reality that was supposed to be vital for me became “catastrophic” and very, very dark. Then, from that time onwards, I lived in such a dark and very dark place because everyone was persecuting me; some wanted my death; I also began to realize that they were persecuting and controlling everything I thought, because I didn't have the peace to even think freely. I felt trapped and totally chained only to my own thoughts, thinking that they were being pursued by everything and everyone.

So the vitality of life which is just the beautiful right to live was *excluded* the. All this because of my free decision, there in my depression, to *be-apart-from-the-world*. Not that this alone generated the psychopathology of the loss of vital contact with reality. But, I, with my daily imaginative daydreams, deep (because very abstract) and secondly, oblivious to everything and everyone, locked away to my mind alone; to the set of my thoughts; This would result and did result (as my psychodiagnosis by the experienced psychiatrist recently attested), a *severe schizoaffective disorder*.

Schizo+affectivity= loss of vital contact with reality. In other words, due to all the transformations in my internal world fueled only by my own thoughts and completely oblivious to every activity and every external act, I significantly lost the vitality of the movement of ordinary confused life. My external being already confused, worse yet I was trapped and surrounded only by inner confusions in the unfathomable abyss of my fantasies. I remember, as today, as even space *appeared to me* confused from me to him because, for me, I saw people's thoughts “move” in the moving spatial fabric. Even the spatiality of the world caused me fear, anguish and even agony at times. Get one *agoraphobia* which seriously extended to manic-depressive episodes and even persecution psychoses.

Currently, six months after the psychodiagnosis of schizoaffective disorder and based on medicines such as Lithium Carbonate; Sertraline Hydrochloride and Risperidone, I started to restrain myself, to start interacting with the world around me again, to write again which is something I really enjoy, to think about relocating myself in a new job and, most importantly and most importantly, Importantly, especially for me, I went back to thinking FREELY about how I dreamed of this happening one day.

Today, I am the author of 11 books in the areas of Philosophy, Phenomenology, Phenomenological Psychopathology, Daseinsanalyse and Esotericism. The resulting issue is that, on the one hand, I suffered a lot when I started to almost completely lose my vital contact with reality, but, on the other hand, all this “psychopathology” made me go beyond the obvious, the superfluous or the ordinary. , by gaining a good amount of knowledge, both practical and theoretical.

In esoteric philosophy there is a universal law that says - “every seven years a cycle is completed”. Today, here I am in the fifth cycle and I feel very accomplished. Today, I am a Christian and my current goal is to pray at least 500 Hail Marys a day. Some will think that this must be a new type of psychosis. But, I think, with all certainty, that this simple act will, someday, be my eternal salvation from this dark, confusing and very nebulous world!

Conclusion

By way of conclusion, we cannot conclude anything simply because this article was just a simple observation and analysis of Minkowski's article as a whole - *The notion of loss of vital contact with reality and its applications in psychopathology*. In the first two topics we present our general view of the topic and, in the third topic, for in-depth analysis, we show the self-analysis of the author of this article when experiencing and experiencing such psychopathology. The only thing that we can confirm about this specific subject and come to conclude in some way is that the loss of vital contact with reality, being a characteristic of schizophrenia and other psychoses, can affect everyone. In the case of the author of this article it was due, above all, to the extraordinary excess of introspection and others that may have come to affect him due to other types of causes, which are various and even infinite. Because as we exist, we are thinking and thinking, we are meaning. Thus, with space and time as absolute categories of the world, our relationship with them is inevitable and it is, precisely, within this relationship and only this, that something will be said about the individual's being, whether pathological or not. May we grow as human beings even in “psychic deformities”, because these “deformities” want to teach us something(s).

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